

A Scoping Quantification of the IPCC's *Sixth Assessment Report* for the Purpose of Using the Text Corpus in a Knowledge Graph

The seven main reports of IPCC's *Sixth Assessment Report* were examined with respect to a number of quantifiable aspects, including: author lists, word count, references, data, glossary terms, and acronyms, etc.

Summary: A report on quantify the IPCC's *Sixth Assessment Report* corpus, as step one, for the software development project to creating a knowledge graph to hold the report text corpus. The objective of this step in the development process is to establish the scale and scope of what is to be included in the knowledge graph.

Keywords: IPCC, Sixth Assessment Report, AR6, climate change, semantic publishing, linked open data, Wikibase, Wikidata, MediaWiki, knowledge graph, climate knowledge graph, semanticclimate

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By Climate Knowledge Graph (CKG) project: <https://tibhannover.github.io/climate-knowledge-graph/>

About CKG project: An R&D project to make a *knowledge graph* of the open access parts of the 10,000 page IPCC's *Sixth Assessment Report* corpus.

GitHub repository: <https://github.com/TIBHannover/climate-knowledge-graph>

Short title: Report Quantifying AR6

Type of report: Software development project report

Report series: CKG build #1 TIB Innofunds (July 2025-June 2026)

Report series Zenodo (ckg-report-series-1):

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Development roadmap

1. Scoping
 1. **Quantify report corpus (this report)**
 2. Report structure
 3. Typesetting requirements for CKG system (CSS Paged Media)
2. Data modelling
 1. Create corpus data model
 2. Document data source addresses and collect data pre-import
 3. Wikibase testing (prototype ideas)
3. RfCs – Overall system; Wikibase, and Data model (specific to Wikibase and LOD)
4. Import
 1. Build text import Selenium module for CPS Impress
 2. Define scope of corpus import
 3. Build Selenium Scrape for AR6 text
 4. Import AR6 text and supporting data into Wikibase
5. Output: Annotation and publishing
 1. Enable Wikibase annotation features for IPCC and community: #semanticClimate; TIB terminology service; ORKG Reborn. (proof of concept)
 2. AR6 report presentation in MediaWiki
 3. Search in MediaWiki
 4. Search, review, and publish (proof of concept)
 5. Publication deposits: TIB Renate, TIB Open Publishing (scoping/proof of concept)

Motivation

The motivation for the exercise was to establish the extent to which the development of a knowledge graph would take shape from the reports.

Description

In the absence of a comprehensive quantitative analysis of the main reports of the IPCC's *Sixth Assessment Report (AR6)*, the initial steps have been taken to compile a set of figures to gain a clearer understanding of the scope of these reports.

As this preliminary round of data collection was partly based on manual counts and estimates, it will be necessary to complement and validate the figures through automated methods in a subsequent phase.

Findings

It is important to note these are preliminary scoping figures.

Item	Count	Status
Number of main reports	7	Definitive
Open access license	6	Definitive
Report DOIs (top level)	7	Good
Page count	10,047	Approx.
Word count	8,047,000	Approx.
Authors	1,106	Approx. *
References	48,400	Approx. *
SYR Notes	-	To be confirmed
Figures	1,672	Approx.
Data	66,834	Approx. *
Glossary terms	925	Good
Acronyms	3041	Approx. *
Index terms	5463	Approx. *
Translations	See: methods	
Wikidata entries (report top level)	13	Approx.
Wikidata entries - data types	-	To be confirmed

Table 1: Summary of IPCC Assessment Report Six quantification. Provisional figures. *Contains duplicates

Further work

An automated count will be carried out using [TIB Grobi](#) software in Q1 2026.

Methods

The methods varied from task to task. For some figures, it was possible to find repositories to draw figures from, while in other cases we approximated figures in order to obtain an estimate.

See full detail on methods in the appendix: Appendix 1 - Data gathering and methods notebook.

Appendix

Appendix 1 - AR6 quantification - Data gathering and methods notebook.

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17521819](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17521819)

Data and resources

Quantification summary as csv and xlsx files. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.17521935](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17521935)

Links and references

Links

IPCC Report website: <https://www.ipcc.ch/reports/>

Website for AR6: <https://www.ipcc.ch/assessment-report/ar6/>

IPCC Authors' repository <https://apps.ipcc.ch/report/authors/authors.php>

IPCC glossary browser <https://apps.ipcc.ch/glossary/>

IPCC Data browser <https://ipcc-data.org/ar6landing.html>

Wikipedia articles on reports:

Wikipedia on WGI https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IPCC_Sixth_Assessment_Report#WG1report

Wikipedia on WGII_

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IPCC_Sixth_Assessment_Report#Working_Group_2_report_\(impacts,_adaptation_and_vulnerability\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IPCC_Sixth_Assessment_Report#Working_Group_2_report_(impacts,_adaptation_and_vulnerability))

Wikipedia on WGIII_

[https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IPCC_Sixth_Assessment_Report#Working_Group_3_report_\(mitigation_of_climate_change\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/IPCC_Sixth_Assessment_Report#Working_Group_3_report_(mitigation_of_climate_change))

Wikipedia on SR1.5_

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Special_Report_on_Global_Warming_of_1.5_%C2%BC

Wikipedia on SRCCCL

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Special_Report_on_Climate_Change_and_Land

Wikipedia on SROCC_

https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Special_Report_on_the_Ocean_and_Cryosphere_in_a_Changing_Climate

References

References in Zotero group:

<https://www.zotero.org/groups/2437020/semanticclimate/collections/SN3LG2KZ/tags/ckg%20report%20quantification/collection>

Chavelli, Félix, and Sarah Connors. 2023. 'Guest Post: What 13,500 Citations Reveal about the IPCC's Climate Science Report'. *CarbonBrief*, March 16. <https://www.carbonbrief.org/guest-post-what-13500-citations-reveal-about-the-ipccs-climate-science-report/>.

Spera, Stephanie. 2021. '234 Scientists Read 14,000+ Research Papers to Write the IPCC Climate Report – Here's What You Need to Know and Why It's a Big Deal'. *The Conversation*, May 8.

<https://theconversation.com/234-scientists-read-14-000-research-papers-to-write-the-ipcc-climate-report-heres-what-you-need-to-know-and-why-its-a-big-deal-165587>.